

Investigating Perceptual Thresholds for Faces and Houses Using

A General Linear Model Approach

Öner, B.¹, Damirchi, R.A.², Noughabi, A.M.V.³, Hnazaee, M.F.⁴

¹ Physics Department, Boğaziçi University, Istanbul, Turkey

² Biomedical Engineering, Islamic Azad University Science and Research Branch, Tehran, Iran

³ School of Psychology, University of East London, London, UK

⁴ Centre for Human Neuroimaging, University College London, London, United Kingdom

Keywords: Face recognition, Visual noise, General Linear Models (GLMs), Neural dynamics

Abstract

This study investigates how perceptual thresholds for recognising faces and houses differ under varying levels of visual noise, using a General Linear Model (GLM) framework. We examine how individual electrode locations and their corresponding anatomical regions contribute to perceptual thresholds by analysing electrocorticography (ECoG) data. Channel-specific analyses reveal localised brain activity highly correlated with task performance, offering new perspectives on neural selectivity and perceptual robustness. Additionally, we compare GLM approach implementations using Python and MATLAB to evaluate differences in efficiency, accuracy, and analytical insights across computational platforms. This comparison highlights how analytical tools can influence the interpretation of neural data.

1. Description

The human brain exhibits remarkable specialisation in processing socially and biologically critical stimuli, such as faces, compared to non-salient objects like houses. This prioritisation is facilitated by dedicated neural circuits, with the Fusiform Face Area (FFA) serving a critical role in facial recognition and the Lingual Gyrus (Figure 1b) involved in processing objects and scenes (Pitcher et al., 2011; Kanwisher et al., 1997). Research has shown that the FFA is particularly adept at processing complex visual stimuli, including faces, even under challenging conditions (Haxby et al., 2002). This specialisation suggests an evolutionary advantage, as recognising faces carries significant social implications.

While previous studies have mapped the roles of these brain regions in static conditions, the dynamics of how they respond to degraded sensory input, such as visual noise, remain poorly understood (Zheng & Liu, 2021). This gap is critical as quantifying perceptual thresholds under noisy environments can provide essential insights into the resilience and adaptability of face-processing neural systems. In this context, perceptual thresholds refer to the contrast values derived from the first-level GLM that quantify the neural activation required to distinguish face vs. house stimuli under varying levels of visual noise. For instance, understanding how the brain manages face recognition amidst visual disturbances can inform both basic neuroscience and applied fields such as artificial vision and assistive technology. (Hassaballah & Aly, 2015)

In this study, we investigate the neural mechanisms underlying perceptual thresholds for faces and houses using electrocorticography (ECoG) data from seven human participants. By systematically varying visual noise levels, we examine how recognition accuracy is affected while capturing neural activity in face-selective (FFA) and object-selective (Lingual Gyrus) regions. To achieve this, we

employ General Linear Models (GLMs) to separate the effects of noise on neural dynamics and behavior, testing two primary hypothesis: (1) Faces exhibit higher perceptual thresholds than houses, reflecting the FFA's evolutionary specialisation for socially salient stimuli, and (2) There is a measurable difference in perceptual thresholds between faces and houses, with faces potentially requiring greater or more robust neural representation under noisy conditions due to their social relevance.

To analyse these effects, we employed two key contrast matrices within the GLM framework. The C2 contrast (Face + House combined response) was designed to assess the general neural activation elicited by both categories, providing insight into overall object recognition processes without distinguishing between them (Quinn et al., 2017). In comparison, the C3 contrast (Faces vs. Houses) specifically measured the difference in neural responses between faces and houses, allowing us to identify potential category-specific processing mechanisms. By applying these contrasts, we extracted contrast of parameter estimates (CoPEs) to quantify perceptual thresholds, helping us determine whether faces or houses required greater neural effort for recognition under varying levels of visual noise.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Participants and Data Acquisition

We analysed ECoG recordings from seven participants drawn from an open-source dataset (Miller et al., 2017). These participants were epileptic patients at Harborview Hospital in Seattle, WA, with electrodes implanted over the frontal, parietal, temporal, and occipital cortex.

2.2 Experimental Tasks

Localizer Task: Participants viewed grayscale images of 50 faces and 50 houses in three experimental runs. Images were presented randomly with a 400-ms inter-stimulus interval. A full description of the task is available in previous studies (Miller et al., 2017; Miller et al., 2015; Miller et al., 2016).

Noisy Task: Participants performed a five-block face-detection task in which they viewed 630 images, comprising faces and houses, embedded in varying levels of visual noise. Noise levels ranged from 0% to 100% in 5% increments. Each image was presented for 1 second, and participants were instructed to press a key whenever they recognised a face.

2.3 Data processing

Data were preprocessed using a notch filter (48–52 Hz, 5th-order Butterworth) to remove line noise. Preprocessing was conducted in MATLAB (SPM toolbox) and Python. Epochs were extracted relative to stimulus onset, and Event-Related Potentials (ERP) analysis was performed by averaging the voltage data in a time window from 300 to 500 milliseconds post-onset. This window was selected to capture activity related to higher-level perceptual processing while minimising early sensory responses.

2.4 First-Level GLM Analysis

We applied a first-level General Linear Model (GLM) analysis to the *noisy task* dataset, modelling neural responses for each participant independently. The design matrix comprised three regressors: an intercept term, a binary indicator for house stimuli, and a binary indicator for face stimuli. This configuration allowed us to assess neural activity associated with each stimulus category while accounting for baseline activation.

To identify general visual responsiveness, we applied the contrast vector $[0.5, 0.5, 0]$, which captures combined activation to both faces and houses. Beta coefficients were estimated for each electrode channel, and contrast of parameter estimates (CoPEs) were computed to quantify activation magnitudes. Within-subject dependent t-tests were performed across trials to determine the statistical significance of activation patterns, enabling us to isolate the most responsive electrode for each participant. This electrode served as the subject-specific region of interest for subsequent group-level analysis. The use of individualised contrast-based localisation aligns with established neuroimaging approaches to functional localisation and random effects modelling (Friston et al., 1995).

2.5 Second-Level GLM Analysis

A second-level GLM analysis was performed across participants to test for group-level effects in neural responses to faces versus houses. For each participant, data from the most significant electrode, identified through the first-level analysis, were aggregated. We then applied a contrast vector of $[1, -1, 0]$ to test whether activation levels differed systematically between face and house stimuli across the cohort. This group-level contrast was used to evaluate our main hypothesis concerning the differential neural encoding of socially salient versus non-social visual stimuli.

2.6 Electrode Selection and Statistical Testing

For each participant, we identified the most significant electrode channel based on neural activation differences between faces and houses. We then tested whether perceptual thresholds differed significantly between categories at both the individual and group levels. Our findings aim to clarify how the brain optimises recognition in noisy environments, offering a computational framework to link neural activity to behavioural outcomes.

3. Results

The most significant electrode channels varied across participants, with five out of seven participants showing peak responses in the Fusiform Gyrus (Figure 1a), supporting its established role in face perception. However, other significant channels were identified in the Parahippocampal Gyrus (Figure 1b), Cuneus (Figure 1c), and Uncus, indicating that object recognition is not confined to a single specialised region but instead involves distributed neural processes. (The perceptual thresholds also varied, with Participant 1 (Parahippocampal Gyrus, -0.0898), Participant 2 (Fusiform Gyrus, 0.1016), and Participant 3 (Uncus, 0.3364) showing distinct responses compared to Participants 4–7, whose thresholds ranged between -0.0849 and -0.0605.

Perceptual thresholds in this study were operationalised as the contrast values extracted from the GLM for each participant's most responsive electrode. (Figure 1) These values represent the magnitude of neural response associated with face versus house recognition under varying levels of visual noise. While the experimental task involved graded noise levels, the GLM itself did not explicitly model noise as a continuous variable. Instead, contrast values were compared across participants to determine whether face or house recognition consistently required greater neural activation.

To determine whether these differences were statistically meaningful at the group level, we conducted a contrast analysis across participants. (Figure 1) The Face vs House Contrast Results yielded a T-value of 0.913 and a P-value of 0.396, indicating no statistically significant distinction in neural responses between the two categories. Similarly, the Perceptual Threshold Comparison resulted in a T-value of 0.164 and a P-value of 0.875, confirming that individual variations were not systematically biased toward faces or houses.

Figure 1. Neural Activation and Perceptual Thresholds in Brain Regions for Face and House Recognition

- a.** Fusiform Gyrus: Associated with face recognition.
- b.** Parahippocampal Gyrus & Lingual Gyrus: Involved in house recognition.
- c.** Cuneus: Plays a role in visual processing related to both faces and houses.

1. Matlab Results 2. Python Results

- A.** Showing contrast values, channels with strong shared activation for houses and faces
- B.** The 3D visualisation provides anatomical context, illustrating electrode locations with their respective contrast values.
- C.** Perceptual thresholds for recognising faces vs. houses across all participants

4. Discussion

Our findings suggest that perceptual thresholds for recognising faces and houses vary widely across individuals, with some showing stronger neural selectivity for faces and others for houses. This

variability may reflect differences in neural architecture, prior experience, or cognitive strategies used for object recognition. These results indicate that there was no significant difference in perceptual thresholds for recognising faces versus houses at the group level. While individual participants showed variability in neural selectivity, this did not translate into a systematic effect across the sample. This finding challenges the assumption that face-processing regions always confer an advantage in perceptual thresholds and suggests that object recognition strategies may be more individualised than previously thought.

Notably, multiple participants exhibited their most significant electrodes in the Fusiform Gyrus, a region known to be critical for face perception. However, the presence of significant channels in object-processing areas, such as the Parahippocampal Gyrus and Cuneus, reinforces the idea that perception is a network-driven process rather than a function of isolated brain regions.

4.1 Comparison with Prior Research

Previous research (Miller et al., 2017) has demonstrated that the FFA is highly specialised for face processing, but our results indicate that this selectivity does not always translate into significantly lower perceptual thresholds for faces. The presence of significant responses in object-processing areas suggests that visual categorisation is a more distributed and context-dependent process than traditionally assumed.

4.2 Limitations and Future Directions

While this study provides novel insights into perceptual thresholds, several limitations should be noted. The small sample size of seven participants limits the generalizability of our findings, as individual differences may not be fully representative of the broader population. Additionally, variability in electrode placement across participants introduces potential inconsistencies in neural recordings, as different cortical areas may be sampled with varying levels of accuracy. Future research

should include larger sample sizes, additional visual noise manipulations, and alternative analytical approaches, such as representational similarity analysis (RSA), to further refine our understanding of how perceptual thresholds vary across individuals and task conditions. (Kriegeskorte et al., 2008)

5. Acknowledgements

We gratefully acknowledge the support of the Impact Scholars Program, the Neuromatch Academy, and the Computational Neuroscience Program. We would also like to express our sincere appreciation to our former teaching assistant, Marta Lotka, and former team member, Elizaveta Kozhanova, for their invaluable contributions to this project.

References

1. Pitcher, D., Walsh, V., & Duchaine, B. (2011). The role of the occipital face area in the cortical face perception network. *Experimental Brain Research*, 209(4), 481–493.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00221-011-2579-1>
2. Kanwisher, N., McDermott, J., & Chun, M. M. (1997). The fusiform face area: A module in human extrastriate cortex specialized for face perception. *Journal of Neuroscience*, 17(11), 4302–4311. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.17-11-04302.1997>
3. Haxby, J. V., Hoffman, E. A., & Gobbini, M. I. (2002). Human neural systems for face recognition and social communication. *Biological Psychiatry*, 51(1), 59–67.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0006-3223\(01\)01330-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0006-3223(01)01330-0)
4. Zheng, X., & Liu, J. (2021). Neural mechanism of noise affecting face recognition. *NeuroImage*, 224, Article 117414. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2020.117414>
5. Hassaballah, M., & Aly, S. (2015). Face recognition: Challenges, achievements, and future directions. *IET Computer Vision*, 9(4), 614–626. <https://doi.org/10.1049/iet-cvi.2014.0084>

6. Haxby, J. V., Hoffman, E. A., & Gobbini, M. I. (2002). Distributed and overlapping representations of faces and objects in ventral temporal cortex. *Science*, 293(5539), 2425–2430. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1063736>
7. Hermes, D., Miller, K. J., Wandell, B. A., & Winawer, J. (2019). Human visual cortical gamma reflects natural image structure. *NeuroImage*, 200, 635–643. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2019.06.017>
8. Lee, Y., Anaki, D., Grady, C. L., & Moscovitch, M. (2012). Neural correlates of temporal integration in face recognition: An fMRI study. *NeuroImage*, 61(4), 1287–1299. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2012.02.073>
9. Miller, K. J., Hermes, D., Pestilli, F., Wig, G. S., & Ojemann, J. G. (2017). Face percept formation in human ventral temporal cortex. *Journal of Neurophysiology*, 118(5), 2614–2627. <https://doi.org/10.1152/jn.00113.2017>
10. Quinn, A. J., Atkinson, L. Z., Gohil, C., Kohl, O., Pitt, J., Zich, C., Nobre, A. C., & Woolrich, M. W. (2017). The GLM-spectrum: A multilevel framework for spectrum analysis with covariate and confound modeling. *NeuroImage*, 153, 250–267. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2017.03.021>
11. Miller, K. J., Hermes, D., Witthoft, N., Rao, R. P., & Ojemann, J. G. (2015). The physiology of perception in human temporal lobe is specialized for contextual novelty. *Journal of Neurophysiology*, 114(1), 256–263. <https://doi.org/10.1152/jn.00118.2015>
12. Miller, K. J., Schalk, G., Hermes, D., Ojemann, J. G., & Rao, R. P. N. (2016). Spontaneous decoding of the timing and content of human object perception from cortical surface recordings reveals complementary information in the event-related potential and broadband spectral

change. PLoS Computational Biology, 12(1), Article e1004660.

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1004660>

13. Miller, K. J., Hermes, D., Pestilli, F., Wig, G. S., & Ojemann, J. G. (2017). Face percept formation in human ventral temporal cortex. *Journal of Neurophysiology*, 118(5), 2614–2627.
<https://doi.org/10.1152/jn.00113.2017>
14. Friston, K.J., Holmes, A.P., Worsley, K.J., Poline, J.P., Frith, C.D., & Frackowiak, R.S.J. (1995). Statistical parametric maps in functional imaging: A general linear approach. *Human Brain Mapping*, 2(4), 189–210. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hbm.460020402>
15. Kriegeskorte, N., Mur, M., & Bandettini, P. A. (2008). Representational similarity analysis – connecting the branches of systems neuroscience. *Frontiers in Systems Neuroscience*, 2, 4. <https://doi.org/10.3389/neuro.06.004.2008>